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The effect of parenthood on doctoral student’s academic socialization and research productivity¹

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Introduction

Doctoral education has adapted to the changing political climate in academia in many countries, emphasizing competitiveness, output, and excellence (Jones 2013). The monograph has been replaced by the compilation thesis in many fields (Mason 2018). Peer-reviewed publications during doctoral studies are viewed as important merits in the competition for funding and employment in the early career (Mason 2018). It follows that obstacles for doctoral students’ academic socialization and scientific performance will have a greater impact on doctoral student’s dissertation work and career prospects. One such obstacle is parenthood.

Today, doctoral students are older and more likely to be female. Previous generations may have postponed parenthood, but postponement may neither be possible nor desirable for current generations (Mirick & Wladkowski 2018). Doctoral students who are parents, in particular mothers, report fewer opportunities for academic socialization and lower research performance and may therefore graduate with less merits and have poorer career prospects compared to non-parents (Kulp 2016; Mirick, & Wladkowski 2018).

Parenthood is one of the main explanations of gender differences in performance and career development in academia (European Commission 2012). Women doctoral students report fewer opportunities for professional development, e.g., publications, to co-author with their supervisor and peers, presenting at conferences, that are important for developing necessary knowledge, skills, social values and networks for a successful entry into the academic career (Kulp 2016; Mirick, & Wladkowski 2018).

A better understanding of how parenthood affects doctoral student outcomes and how parenthood is related gender differences is important since (1) previous research have shown that gender differences arise already during doctoral studies (Feldon et al., 2017; Lindahl, Colliander, & Danell 2021); and (2) parents are an understudied and growing group (Wladkowski & Mirick, 2019).

This paper reports two studies based on a sample of 868 doctoral students in Sweden that started 2016, 2017, or 2018. Sweden provides a great opportunity to examine effects of parenthood

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since the group of doctoral students who are parents is large compared with other countries (Gröjer et al., 2016; Wladkowski & Mirick, 2019).

The purpose of the studies is to provide insights into how parenthood affects doctoral students' academic socialisation and research productivity. For this purpose, four hypothesis and a research question were formulated:

Hypothesis 1: Parenthood has a negative effect on academic socialisation during doctoral studies.

Hypothesis 2: Parenthood has a negative effect on research productivity during doctoral studies.

Hypothesis 3: The negative effect of parenthood is stronger for women than men.

Hypothesis 4: The effect of parenthood differs between fields of research.

Research question: To which extent is differences in productivity between parent and non-parent doctoral students related to (a) co-authoring with their supervisors; and (b) attending conferences with their supervisors?

Data collection and method

Data was collected from three sources: (1) employment data at 27 Swedish Higher Education Institutions (HEI); (2) SwePub, the national repository for academic publications in Sweden; and (3) a web survey that was distributed in the beginning of June 2021 to all doctoral students employed at the 27 HEIs in Sweden during February and Mars 2021. This study is based on a subset of respondents from the survey ($n = 868$) that started their doctoral studies between 2016 and 2018 in the research areas Medical and Health sciences, Natural sciences, and Engineering and Technology. For each doctoral student measures were taken from the start year up until 2020. The data set was also restricted to male or female students who are writing a compilation thesis. Register data from UKÄ (i.e., The Swedish Higher Education Authority) on doctoral students who started their studies between 2016 and 2018 in Sweden was used to assess the representativity of the sample. The number of doctoral students that started between 2016 and 2018 in the three targeted research areas at the 27 HEIs was 7439, which gives an approximate response rate of 12%. Table 1 show how register data from UKÄ and the sample compare on some key variables, i.e., research area, sex, and age.

Table 1. Comparison of percent of frequencies over key variables.

	UKÄ %	Sample %
Natural sciences	30.38	37.79
Engineering and Technology	26.55	26.84
Medical and Health sciences	43.07	35.37
Man	54.46	45.85
Women	45.54	54.15
Age < 30	57.39	66.94
Age 30-39	30.65	27.42
Age > 39	11.96	5.65

A Swedish report based on data from 2014 and 2015 (Gröjer et al., 2016) indicates that 24% of doctoral students in the natural sciences had children under the age of 18 living at home. In this

study parents with children under the age of 18 in natural sciences in this study is 22%. Comparing the sample and the population indicate similar distributions over some key variables.

Variables

The main predictor in this study is an operationalization of parenthood: a dummy where the value 1 denotes that the doctoral student is parent of at least one child children under the age of 18. Coding: *Parent*.

The effect of parenthood is analysed on four different dependent variables. Three dependent variables measure aspects of academic socialisation and was collected with the web survey. These three dependent variables were constructed based on theories of academic socialization (Weidman et al. 2001; Paglis et al., 2006). This study focuses on a specific aspect of academic socialization – co-authoring and collaborating with the supervisor. The three dependent variables focusing on academic socialization are:

(1) Co-authoring with supervisors was collected with a question asking for the number of manuscripts/publications of academic character the doctoral student has co-authored with his or her supervisors from the beginning of doctoral studies up until 2020. Coding: *Co-authoring with supervisors*.

(2) Number of conferences together with supervisors collected with a question asking for how many conferences the doctoral student has attended together with his or her supervisors, where either the doctoral student or the supervisors presented research they had collaborated on, since the beginning of doctoral studies up until 2020. Coding: *Nr. conferences with supervisors*.

(3) Number of conferences was collected with the web survey asking for how many conferences the doctoral student had attended from the beginning of doctoral studies up until 2020. Coding: *Nr. conferences*.

The fourth dependent variable was collected from SwePub operationalize research productivity, i.e., the number of publications during doctoral studies. Publications was collected from the start of doctoral studies up until 2020. Coding: *Nr. of publications during doctoral studies*.

Nine additional variables were constructed:

1. Sex: A dummy where the value 1 denotes man and 0 denotes women. Coding: *Man*.
2. Male supervisor: A dummy where 1 indicates that the main supervisor is male. Coding: *Male supervisor*.
3. Age: A continuous variable denoting the age at beginning of doctoral studies. Coding: *Age*.
4. Conscientiousness: Operationalizing conscientiousness, which is measured with three facets from the 4-item IPIP scales (Johnson 2014): Self-efficacy; Achievement-striving; and Self-discipline. The predictor was constructed by summing all items. It is treated as a continuous variable in the analyses. Coding: *Conscientiousness*.
5. Number of publications before doctoral studies: A continuous variable denoting the number of publications up until the start year of doctoral studies. Coding: *Nr. publications pre-doctoral studies*.
6. Part of research group: A dummy where the value 1 indicates that the doctoral student conducts his or her thesis work as a part of a research group. Coding: *Research group*.

7. Research area: A categorical variable constructed to adjust for differences between research areas (Schubert & Braun 1986; Becher 1994). The categories are: Engineering and technology; Natural sciences; and Medical and Health sciences. Coding: *Research area*.
8. Start year: A categorical variable denoting the year the doctoral student started doctoral studies. Coding: *Start year*.
9. Nr. of months of doctoral student employment: A continuous variable denoting the number of months from the start of the doctoral employment up until 2020. Doctoral students start their education at different dates. This variable is constructed to approximate and adjust for such time differences among the doctoral students. Coding: *Nr. of month of doctoral employment*.

Method

Multiple negative binomial regression is used to conduct the analysis since the dependent variables are count variables (Hilbe, 2014). Overall, 12.2% of the doctoral students has missing values on one or more variables ($n = 106$). Multiple imputation with chained equations was used to handle missing values in the models (Enders, 2010).

Results and discussion

The effect of parenthood on co-authoring with supervisors and attending conferences

Table 2 report results for testing Hypothesis 1 where it is expected that parenthood has a negative effect on co-authoring with the supervisors and attending conferences during doctoral studies. Table 2 presents the negative binomial coefficients for Model 1, 2, and 3 focusing on academic socialisation.

The main predictor of interest is *Parent*. In Table 2 the coefficients for *Parent* show negative effects and statistical significance ($p < 0.05$) in all three models. These results support Hypothesis 1 since a negative effect indicate that parents have co-authored less and participated in fewer conferences, compared with non-parents. To get an indication of the effect sizes, average partial effects (Hilbe 2014) was calculated for the predictor *Parent* (Table 3).

Table 2. Three multiple negative binomial regression models.

	Model 1: Co-authoring with supervisors	Model 2: Nr. conferences	Model 3: Nr. conferences with supervisors
	Coefficient	Coefficient	Coefficient
Parent	-0.185**	-0.289***	-0.306***
Man	0.089	-0.010*	-0.078
Age	0.000	-0.001	0.001
Conscientiousness	0.018***	0.005	0.009
Male supervisor	0.216***	-0.039	-0.044
Research group	0.088*	0.102*	0.197**
Nr. of month of doctoral employment	0.002	0.003	0.005
Research area	YES	YES	YES
Start year	YES	YES	YES
Intercept	-0.288	1.254***	-0.390
Pseudo-R ²	0,054	0,057	0.033

Note. * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$.

The average partial effect for *Parent* is -0.500 in Model 1 (Table 3). This means that parents have, on average, about 0.5 fewer co-authored manuscripts/publications compared with non-parent doctoral students, while holding the other variables in the model at their mean (Hilbe 2014). Parents also, on average, participate in about 0.861 fewer conferences, and 0.517 fewer conferences where the student or the supervisor present work they have been collaborating on.

Table 3. Average partial effects for *Parent* in Model 1, 2, and 3 (from Table 2).

	Average partial effects	P-value	95% CI
Model 1: Co-authoring with supervisors	-0.500	0.003	-0.829 -0.170
Model 2: Nr. conferences	-0.861	<0.001	-1.190 -0.532
Model 3: Nr. conferences with supervisors	-0.517	<0.001	-0.790 -0.243

Hypothesis 3 and 4 was tested by including interactions between *Parent* and *Man*, and between *Parent* and *Research area*. No significant or relevant interactions could be found in the models (these are not reported). Hypothesis 3 and 4 was therefore not supported in the case of academic socialisation, indicating that the negative effect of parenthood is similar for men and women and similar over research areas.

The effect of parenthood on research productivity

Table 4 report results for testing Hypothesis 2 where it is expected that parenthood has a negative effect on research productivity during doctoral studies, and the research question where it is asked to which extent differences in productivity between parents and non-parents are related to co-authoring and attending conferences with their supervisors. In Model II and III the variables *Co-authoring with supervisors* and *Nr. of conferences with supervisors* are added to Model I to examine how the variable *Parent* change. As can be seen in Table 4 the coefficient for *Parent* is statistically significant ($P < 0.05$) and the effect is negative in Model I. This result support Hypothesis 2 since it indicates that parents publish fewer peer reviewed journal articles than non-parents. When the variable *Co-authoring with supervisors* is added (Model II) the coefficient for *Parent* becomes non-significant and is reduced from -0.257 to -.128. Parent is further reduced to -0.105 in Model III. This indicates that co-authoring and attending conferences with supervisors partly explain why parents publish less during doctoral education compared with non-parents. These results are in line with Lindahl, Colliander and Danell (2021) where it is shown that the gender gap in productivity during doctoral studies to a large extent can be explained by the extent to which doctoral students are co-authoring with the supervisor. An interesting finding in this paper is that a similar pattern for doctoral student parents is indicated.

Table 4. Three multiple negative binomial regression models and their coefficients. Dependent variable is *Nr. of publications during doctoral studies*.

	Model I	Model II	Model III
	Coefficient	Coefficient	Coefficient
Parent	-0.255*	-0.141	-0.112
Man	0.070	0.000	0.010
Age	-0.020	-0.021*	-0.022*
Conscientiousness	0.015*	0.008	0.007
Nr. publications pre-doctoral studies	0.341***	0.293***	0.288***
Research group	0.414***	0.344***	0.317***
Nr. of month of doctoral employment	0.016*	0.015*	0.012
Research area	YES	YES	YES
Start year	YES	YES	YES
Co-authoring with supervisors	-	0.128***	0.120***
Nr. conferences with supervisors	-	-	0.049*
Intercept	-0.768	-0.897	-0.829**
Pseudo-R ²	0,082	0,105	0.106

Note. * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$.

The average partial effect for *Parent* is -0.272 in Model I (Table 5). This means that parents have published, on average, 0.272 fewer peer reviewed articles compared with non-parent doctoral students, while holding the other variables in the model at their mean. When *Co-authoring with supervisors* is added, the average marginal effect is reduced to -0.162 and when *Nr. of conferences with supervisors* is added the average marginal effect is further reduced to -0.129 (table 5).

Table 5. Average partial effects for *Parent* in Model I, II, and III (from Table 4).

	Average partial effects	P-value	95% CI
Model I	-0.274	0.023	-0.509 -0.039
Model II + <i>Co-authoring with supervisors</i>	-0.162	0.196	-0.409 -0.084
Model III + <i>Co-authoring with supervisors</i> + <i>Nr. of conferences with supervisors</i>	-0.129	0.306	-0.376 0.118

Hypothesis 3 and 4 was tested by including interactions between *Parent* and *Man*, and between *Parent* and *Research area*. No significant and relevant interactions could be found (these models not reported in this paper). Hypothesis 3 and 4 could therefore not be supported. The finding that the negative effect of parenthood is similar for male and female doctoral students seem counterintuitive since doctoral student mothers are reported as a particularly vulnerable group in the literature (Mirick, & Wladkowski 2018). However, these results are in line with Kulp (2016). The mixed results in the literature may depend on between-country differences.

Conclusions

Overall, the results indicate (1) that doctoral student parents co-author less with their supervisors, attend fewer conferences (i.e., academic socialization), and have lower research productivity, than non-parents; (2) that the negative effect of parenthood on academic socialization and research productivity is similar for men and women and also similar over research areas (i.e., Medical and Health sciences, Natural sciences, and Engineering and

Technology); and (3) that differences in productivity between parent and non-parent doctoral students are related to co-authoring and attending conferences with their supervisors.

Limitations and future research

A limitation with the study is the non-random sample and the response rate. However, the indications of similarity between the sample and the population some key variables provide indications of representativity. The similar pattern compared with previous research (i.e., Lindahl, Colliander & Danell, 2021; Kulp 2016) further strengthens this indication.

While this study indicates that there are substantial differences between parents and non-parent doctoral students in terms of collaborating with the supervisor, attending conferences and publish peer-reviewed articles, potential explanations for these differences has not been examined. One explanation could be that parents have more study breaks due to, e.g., sick leave or parental leave. Another explanation could be that parents, due to care responsibilities, have less time to devote to work than non-parents. Examining potential explanations for the observed differences are tasks for future research.

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